

MOVING Final Conference: A future for mountain areas in post-2027 priorities

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

13 - 14 June 2024

On June 13 and 14, the MOVING Final Conference: “A Future for Mountain Areas in Post-2027 EU Priorities” took place in Brussels, marking the culmination of a four-year journey for the project. This two-day high-level event gathered over 70 participants from European Institutions (**European Parliament, European Commission, European Economic and Social Committee**), EU supported organisations (**ESPON, Joint Research Centre, Rural Pact Support Office**), EU stakeholder groups (**Euromontana, AREPO**), research community and local/regional mountain actors to underscore the crucial role of mountain areas in advancing Europe’s political objectives and targets by 2030.

Organised by the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL) and hosted by AREPO within the framework of the EU-funded H2020 MOVING project (MOUNTAIN VALORISATION THROUGH INTERCONNECTEDNESS AND GREEN GROWTH), the event was strategically timed to discuss the pivotal role of mountains and mountain value chains in achieving Europe’s political targets by 2030 and shaping the post-2027 EU political agenda.

Objectives of the conference:

- To illustrate the key role of mountain and rural areas, with a focus on value chains, achieving Europe’s political objectives and targets by 2030.
- Present tools, solutions and policies to increase the resilience and sustainability of rural and mountainous communities.
- Present the MOVING Policy Roadmap and its final recommendations to unlock the power of mountain value chains and contribute to sustainable mountain development.
- Discuss MOVING’s contribution to the EU’s [Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas](#) and the EU’s post-2027 policies.

ORGANISER:

13 - 14 JUNE 2024

BRUSSELS, BELGIUM

70 PARTICIPANTS
(EU institutions, research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, etc.)

19 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS [HERE](#)

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Key take-aways:

- The MOVING project provided evidence on [cross-country challenges and solutions](#) to move towards resilience Mountain Value Chains, based on the [participatory work](#) on 23 partners and 23 Mountain Regions.
- Climate change impacts are perceived as the biggest threat to Mountain Value Chains in the future. The interwovenness of climate impacts with depopulation, lack of skills, and lack of integrated policies is seen as a worsening factor of climate-related challenges in most MOVING regions.
- The MOVING project identified [30 Strategic Options](#), [160 climate adaptation mechanisms](#), [6 upgrading strategies](#) to lead Mountain Value Chains transition towards resilience and sustainability. Other wide solutions are offered by the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (incl. the [Rural Pact](#), [EU Rural Observatory](#)), the EU CAP [Expert Focus Group on Competitive and Resilient Mountain Areas](#), Horizon Europe projects focused on mountains.
- Mountain Value Chains are key to contribute to Europe's three transitions (green, digital, demographic). **Post-2027** policies should continue to offer earmarking to support mountain areas across its policy portfolios (Cohesion Policy, Common Agricultural Policy, climate, etc.) in line with Art 174 TFEU and the Better Regulation, making it simplified, place-based and multi-level. Capacity-building and simplification should be promoted at national/regional levels to ensure the uptake of those programs and policy solutions into mountain areas.
- The **MOVING Policy Roadmap** provides a framework to promote an integrated approach to mountain policies in the post-2027 period. This framework is built around eight Policy Building Blocks and strongly based on Better Governance and Regulation.

MOVING Project, an Amazing Four-Year Journey

Mar DELGADO

Full Professor at University of Cordoba and MOVING Coordinator

Mar Delgado kicked off the conference by introducing the MOVING project to participants and providing an overview of its achievements over the past four years. Gathering **23 partners and 23 regional case studies**, the MOVING project had the ambitious goal of “**building capacities and co-developing relevant policy frameworks** across Europe for the **establishment of new or upgraded/upscaled Mountain Value Chains** that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas - in a bottom-up participatory process with value chain actors, stakeholders and policy-makers”.

Mountains are the ecological backbone of Europe, representing 30% of the EU surface, serving as water reservoirs, and delivering essential ecosystem services for the socio-economic well-being of highland and lowland communities. Nevertheless, **mountain regions are not sufficiently valued**, which has been the starting point of the MOVING project. The valorisation of mountain territories, including human capital, should be place-based and data-driven, seek to enhance local assets (e.g. knowledge, perceptions, and expectations), and leverage the distinct features of mountain areas.

To this end, the project workflow was structured to first investigate mountain diversity, followed by analysing it to ascertain its potential, and finally defining perspectives for its upgrade. Ms.

Delgado outlined the key results of the MOVING project for each phase, including the **Conceptual Analytical Framework, Inventory with >400 Mountain Value Chains**, the **participatory analysis of land use system vulnerability**, the **Value Chain cross-comparison and benchmarking**, and the **participatory Multilevel Foresight**. The **MOVING Policy Roadmap** and **Final Recommendations** will be available by the end of the project, building on findings from all the project’s phases and case studies across Europe.

In numbers, MOVING developed and animated a **multi-level Community of Practice** consisting of around **1,000 local and regional stakeholders** across its 23 multi-actor platforms in Europe and beyond, and 87 EU-level members. It also involved **over 500 mountain youngsters** to identify their wishes, expectations, and fears for the future of mountains.

“**What legacy does the project leave behind?**”, reflected Ms. Delgado. The MOVING project provided a framework to prioritise listening and amplifying the voices of over 1000 mountain stakeholders and validating scientific results with local knowledge. It demonstrated how mountains’ perceptions can shift from places of constraints to places of opportunities. It also highlighted the need for more granular data and multi-level support to unlock the potential of mountain value chains in the post-2027 EU programming period.

MOVING Community of Practice

Figure 1. MOVING’s Results over the project’s lifetime.

Keynote speech | The long-term vision for EU's rural areas: key achievements & ways forward

Mario MILOUCHEV

Director at Directorate D "CAP Strategic Plans II", DG AGRI, European Commission

"Rural and mountain areas hold immense significance for the Commission due to their human, social, and environmental capital, as well as their natural beauty"

Mario Milouchev

Mario Milouchev started by presenting the [EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas](#) (LTVRA) and its latest developments. Three years later since its adoption in June 2021, the European Commission published two staff working documents in 2024: '[Taking stock of Rural Action Plan implementation](#)' and the '[Reviewed EU Rural Action Plan](#)'. The stocktaking report draws results from the implementation of the Vision over the previous 3 years and sets the forthcoming steps for the years to come through the Vision's Rural Action Plan and Rural Pact.

As he underlined, these documents follow the publication of other reports contributing to EU rural policies, including the **2023-2027 CAP Study reports** (on September and November 2023), the '**Summary of CAP Strategic Plans for 2023-27: joint effort and collective ambition**', the **2021-2027 Cohesion Policy Report** (May 2023) and the collection of practices (March 2024).

The 24 actions and 6 cross-cutting actions of the LTVRA have all been initiated and led to some initial results, which were presented by Mr. Milouchev, including the launch of the [Rural Revitalisation Platform](#), specific funding for rural projects, the [Rural Toolkit](#) for funding in rural areas and the [Rural Observatory](#). Additionally, the **Rural Pact** now counts approximately 2,500 members and 120

commitments to act. He underscored that the Commission will continue to sustain rural areas and deliver the LTVRA measures in the post-2027 programming period. In this regard, further work will be done in coordination with the Rural Pact Support Office and Rural Pact Coordination Group to accelerate the **Rural Pact implementation in Member States**.

Mr. Milouchev underlined the relevance of MOVING's results and recommendations for the EU's policy cycle, as it aligns with the new collegium of Commissioners, who will make some proposals for post-2027 EU policies. The European Commission is looking into opportunities to collect with stakeholders' views for the future of EU policies, such as the **EU Strategic Dialogue on Agriculture**, or the [10 questions for moving the LTVRA forward](#).

He presented the upcoming milestones leading to the proposal for a post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy, while also highlighting that the CAP alone cannot solve rural inequalities and territorial gaps. To conclude, Mr. Milouchev presented preliminary rural policy problems that emerged in their foresight exercise, which will be pivotal in identifying risks, trends, and opportunities for the future of rural policies.

Challenges in Rural and Mountainous Europe

Nuno GUIOMAR

Researcher, University of Évora

Nuno Guiomar presented findings of the **vulnerability analyses** carried out by MOVING across its 23 Regions, which resulted into **23 spatially explicit datasets** (one per region). He underlined that it is very challenging to assess the vulnerability of mountains, as they are fragile and complex socio-economic systems. In fact, small changes in the drivers of change affecting mountain value chains can produce catastrophic effects on the entire socio-ecological system.

The University of Evora carried out the vulnerability analysis using a **four-step process**: starting with the characterisation of the farming and forestry systems in mountain areas, followed by the assessment of susceptibility in such systems, participatory vulnerability analyses of land systems, and mapping of mountain vulnerabilities.

Finding appropriate datasets that accurately represent the diversity of mountain regions has posed challenges in terms of landscape planning and ecological development. More than 400 spatial datasets were tested. As a result, the MOVING analysis represents the **most comprehensive analysis of the vulnerability of mountain land-use systems** in Europe done to date.

Mr, Guiomar stressed the importance of involving stakeholders in the process to integrate the empirical knowledge of local actors into a more nuanced understanding of the local and spatial dynamics and characteristics that are most determinant for vulnerability. In the MOVING vulnerability analysis, approximately **500 stakeholders were involved in the 23 Regions**. It emerged that **drivers of change and vulnerability are similar across the 23 regions** analysed by MOVING.

Among all, **climatic drivers of change** are seen as the most impactful for all regions, though their impacts are not the same across all regions. For instance, climate change impacts will have more severe consequences in Mediterranean mountain regions while it will contribute to increasing productivity in the Alps. He stressed that, contrary to literature, **land use and land cover change are not the main drivers of change**, while distance from roads and cities, internet quality, and other factors are identified as key drivers of change in the mountains.

Based on the MOVING vulnerability analysis, **160 adaptive mechanisms** were identified across all regions, with most demonstrating high social and environmental feasibility, and moderate technical and economic feasibility.

“Drivers of change are similar across the 23 MOVING mountain regions. Divergently from literature, land use and land cover change are not primary drivers, while distance from roads and cities, internet quality, and others are identified as key influencers of change in mountain areas”

Nuno Guiomar

Mountain Value Chain Contribution to Sustainability and Resilience

Mar DELGADO

Full Professor at University of Cordoba and MOVING Coordinator

“The hypothesis we tested in our cross-comparison analysis is that mountain value chains can increase the sustainability and resilience of mountain areas”

Mar Delgado

Mar Delgado presented the results from their analysis of **mountain value chains' contribution to sustainability and resilience of mountain regions**. This analysis was performed across regions and consistently with the **five thematic clusters** in MOVING: Demographic and Social Aspects (S), Value and Quality Products (V), Innovation and Infrastructure (I), Nature and Ecosystem Services (N), and Territoriality, Cooperation and Governance (G).

A cluster workshop (with regional stakeholders) and an online questionnaire (to experts) were carried out to assess the value chains' contribution to **seven objectives**: human capital, sustainable use of local assets, adaptive capacity, cooperation, inclusiveness, ecological resilience, and attractiveness and well-being.

Results of the cross-case analysis clearly indicate that the **social aspect** is crucial for the sustainability of these value chains. Regional stakeholders particularly prioritised **human capital and cooperation**. Among experts, more than 35% prioritised **socio-ecological balance** as a major priority, and more than 80% recognised the importance of mountain value chains to social-related aspects. As Ms. Delgado stressed, this shows that results from experts are coherent with people's priorities.

Ms. Delgado explained that mountain value chains provide **public and private goods** which are crucial for the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas. The **assemblage of value chains** can contribute further to this objective, but only when value chains are controlled by local actors.

To conclude, Ms. Delgado emphasised that the sustainability and resilience of mountains are conditioned by several social and political aspects. Consumers' capability to recognize and pay for the added value of mountain products and their positive contributions to territorial development should be addressed strategically.

Figure 2. MOVING's five thematic clusters by region.

DAY 1 | 13 JUNE 2024

Round table | Challenges in Rural and Mountainous Europe

Moderated by Gianluca Brunori, University of Pisa

Wiktor SZYDAROWSKI
Director at ESPON EGTC
(European Grouping on
Territorial Cooperation)

Maria GARGANO
Researcher
Egmont Institute

Cristina MICHELONI
VINIDEA and MOVING
Partner

This round table aimed at taking stock of MOVING's results to address challenges experienced by mountain value chains and situating them in a wider picture of trends and challenges shared by Europe's rural areas.

“Climate change is a big challenge for mountain areas, but this is only a side of the coin. The MOVING project shows that depopulation, lack of skills, and lack of integrated policies worsen the resilience of mountains and their productivity backbone: value chains”

Gianluca Brunori

Gianluca Brunori kicked off the discussion by asking about the most pressing challenge affecting mountain territories in our times. Speakers agreed with the results shared by the MOVING analysis and particularly emphasised the **difficulty of attracting skilled talent, diversifying the mountain economy**, and addressing **mountain depopulation** as the most crucial ones. As emphasised

by Ms. Micheloni, mountain depopulation was identified as the most pressing challenge experienced by wine value chains in three MOVING regions, even more so than climatic impacts. Furthermore, Mr Szydarowski from ESPON EGTC stressed the **interwovenness and dynamicity of current challenges, highlighting** the need for concerted and multi-level interventions to prevent mountains from falling into the development trap and to bridge territorial gaps.

Panelists agreed that several policy advancements were made in the last decades to make policies more fitting to the challenges experienced by these territories. In this regard, panelists underscored the **Commission's emphasis on demographics** since 2019 to address Europe's "third transition" on demographic change and decline, as well as the **Cohesion Policy's efforts to overcome the 'silo' approach** through the Integrated Territorial Investments (ITIs), CLLD/LEADER approach, or the functional areas. Furthermore, Mr. Szydarowski underlined that voluntary commitment and social bonding can be used as mechanisms to promote territorial development in addition to legislative frameworks, as illustrated by the town of Saluzzo in Italy.

To conclude, Gianluca Brunori asked panelists to reflect on the **skills needed for mountains to overcome challenges and thrive**. It emerged the need to promote place-specific and diversified skills leveraging specialised knowledge and general skills, particularly social bonding skills. In addition, it was mentioned that skill development should be grounded in an analysis of local needs and assets, as well as territorial know-how.

Community and Business-Driven Solutions from Rural and Mountain Regions

Moderated by Giulia Scaglioni, Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO)

1 | Value Chains for Sustainable Mountain Development: Strategies for Upgrading and Innovation

Kirsty BLACKSTOCK
Social Researcher, James Hutton Institute

Kirsty Blackstock began by describing how value chains are understood in the MOVING project and the influence of green growth and interconnectedness. In MOVING, Mountain Value Chains are defined as **a set of activities** – spanning production, processing, distribution and marketing, and consumption – **required to bring a mountain product or service from the producer to its consumer**. Considering the diversity of backgrounds, MOVING's definition of Value Chain is built around several underpinning theories, such as Porter's competitive advantage theory (1985) and Moretti et al., 2023 sociological approach to 'values'.

Ms. Blackstock explained that value chains interactions originate the so-called '**assemblage**', and the most common examples in the mountains are value chains based on tourism and gastronomic heritage. She also added that these **value chains often extend beyond mountains** and strongly depend on infrastructure and institutions.

Ms. Blackstock highlighted the diversity of value produced in the mountains, spanning from more conventional to modern sectors. Whilst livestock, arable/horticultural, and forestry remain the largest economic uses of mountain regions; **GDP and employment data show that other sectors, including energy, services and tourism, are very important**. She stressed the need for coherence between these different sectors for viable and sustainable mountain development.

“Mountain Value Chains contribute to the objectives of prosperous rural areas, and facilitate stronger and more connected communities”

Kirsty Blackstock

In MOVING, the participatory evaluation of Mountain Value Chains shows that **assemblages bring added economic, social, and environmental added values to these territories**, with the economic benefits being stronger than the social and environmental ones. She also explained that there might be competition for scarce capitals between Value Chains.

Furthermore, Ms. Blackstock provided an overview of **innovation strategies to upgrade or upscale Mountain Value Chains** and some illustrated examples. These **innovation strategies** can be clustered into **six macrogroups**: i) product upgrading, ii) process upgrading, iii) function upgrading, iv) inter-chain upgrading, v) horizontal upgrading, vi) vertical upgrading. Upgrading can be driven by different actors and mechanisms, including consumers-related, market-driven, and state-driven.

2 | Strategic Options, Seeds for Long-term Changes

Dominique BARJOLLE

President at Origin for Sustainability (ORIGIN) and Senior Researcher at ETH Zurich

“We have to help communities to build a long-term vision at community level”

Dominique Barjolle

In her intervention, Dominique Barjolle provided an overview of the **30 MOVING Strategic Options** and the process to define them. She began by explaining that the underlying assumption of the work done was that the essential functions of mountains (conservation and preservation of natural resources; production and heritage; recreation and well-being; geostrategy) are currently endangered by three main threats: climate change, demographic loss, and market disruptions. Among these, the 23 MOVING regional cases show that **market disruption (and consumer demand) is perceived as the strongest threat affecting Mountain Value Chains**. She remarked that the cross-cutting nature of demographic dynamics with local population loss is a factor that affects all the scenarios defined.

In MOVING, the 23 Mountain Regions were asked to visualise a desirable scenario for their future, based on the consideration of such pending threats and other long-term forces. To carry out this exercise, 22 regional foresight and 1 EU-level foresight workshops were organised, leading to **four archetypes depicting reasons for Mountain Value Chains to innovate**: i) economic-driven, ii) nature-driven, niche and diversification, iv) knowledge and innovation. Most MOVING Regions indicated market forces and consumer demand (**economic-drive archetype**) as the most relevant reason for driving change in their Mountain Value Chains.

As Ms. Barjolle explained, “It is necessary to design and implement Strategic Options across multiple dimensions to address challenges, sustain human settlements, secure livelihoods, and protect natural and cultural resources.” The follow-up stage was to identify Strategic Options for Mountain Value Chains within all 23 MOVING Regions. Strategic Options are **inspirational solutions funded through various mechanisms to address mountain-specific challenges**. They can be replicated elsewhere with adjustments, supported by national or European mechanisms. However, complex interventions require local adaptation. For instance, the “Erasmus Altitude” would provide a framework for accelerating the exchange of mountain know-how and relevant experience within thematic networks.

Existing Strategic Options across Europe could better address specific challenges in the mountains, while emerging ones need an assessment of their potential for replication in other regions. Ms. Barjolle concluded with a reflection about how shifting from Strategic Options to policy responses recognises the absence of a one-size-fits-all policy **mix** for addressing all mountain needs. Also, she defended that **policies should improve the framework for supporting the development and implementation of Strategic Options**.

3 | Case Study: Genossenschaft GranAlpin

Chloé BERLI

GrainAlpin and MOVING Regional Partner from the Swiss Alps

Chloé Berli presented **GrainAlpin**, a grain-related cooperative based in the Swiss Alps, which contributed to re-establishing the grain value chains in the region of Grisons.

The Grisons region features a typical alpine landscape that has historically been devoted to grain production. However, between 1930 and 1991, grain fields declined severely due to unprofitability of mountain agriculture and loss of terrace management. In particular, the difficulty of using machinery in mountain slopes was a major barrier to grain production.

In 1987, the cooperative GrainAlpin was created to prevent the disappearance of Grisons mountain grain. Today, this cooperative cultivates **260 hectares compared to over 5,000 in the early 50s**.

The cooperative supports various activities within the value chain and diversifies its buyer base. It also emphasises product labeling to ensure differentiation.

As Ms. Berli highlighted, **main challenges** span across climate-related factors (e.g. extreme weather events, water availability), deficiencies in the value chain (lack of adapted seeds, chain size, grain collection), and more contextual factors (decreasing purchasing power since the end of corona pandemic, infrastructure).

She also underlined that future opportunities might be driven by a diversification of the cooperative's activities, driving higher demand and an increase in ecosystem services.

Figure 3. Cultivation of grain in Ramosch, 1917-2009. Source: Chloé Berli's presentation

DAY 1 | 13 JUNE 2024

Round table | EU-wide Solutions for Rural and Mountain Regions

Moderated by Carla Lostrangio, Rural and Territorial Development Officer, European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Eleftherios STAVROPOULOS
EU Joint Research Centre

Klavdija RAMSAK-NOEMI
DG AGRI
European Commission

Anna GIORGI
Full Professor, University of Milan, Coordinator of the MountResilience project

Carla Lostrangio opened this round table by recalling the audience on the plethora of initiatives, strategies, and tools that have lately been adopted to support rural and mountain area development, beyond those identified by the MOVING project. Examples of these initiatives were represented in the panel by speakers such as the [Rural Observatory](#) and [Rural Toolkit](#) developed by the Joint Research Centre, and the [EU CAP Network Expert Focus Group on 'Competitive and Resilience Mountain Areas'](#).

The discussion began with a question on the added value of such initiatives for mountain actors. Panelists underlined that such initiatives bridge existing gaps in knowledge and equip local actors with inspirational examples.

Mr. Stavropoulos said, "The EU Rural Toolkit to make EU funds understandable and practical to communities, whilst the Rural Observatory provides evidence for better understanding rural dynamics."

Ms. Giorgi, also coordinator of the Horizon Europe MountResilience project, stressed the **role of research to identify and test solutions adapted to local challenges as well as to develop systemic modeling** to improve the competitiveness of mountain areas.

Panelists reflected on existing barriers to access some of these solutions. It was underlined that decision-making at local, regional and national level is often limited to the legislative period. As a result, the search for tangible results within the legislative period hampers long-term strategies and planning. An **integrated bottom-up approach** is needed and should be considered **beyond the legislative period**. This will contribute to a sense of actor ownership of solutions. Ms. Giorgi also emphasised that mountain strategic solutions **extend beyond agriculture**. While characterising mountain agrobiodiversity can help revive traditional products and value chains, comprehensive policies are needed to address the multi-faceted opportunities of mountains.

Round table | Post-2027 EU Policies impacting Rural and Mountainous Areas

Moderated by Serafin Pazos Vidal, Senior Expert in Rural and Territorial Development, European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Toma ŠUTIĆ

Cabinet of Vice President charged with Democracy and Demography, European Commission

Benoit NADLER

DG REGIO European Commission

Orsolya FRIZON SOMOGYI

DG AGRI European Commission

Lidija PAVIĆ-ROGOŠIĆ

European Economic and Social Committee

This round table aimed at contributing to the **ongoing discussions shaping European policies over the next programming period and their implications for future mountain territorial development.**

Serafin Pazos-Vidal opened this round table by recalling the upcoming milestones in the EU policy cycle – including the European Parliament’s elections, the appointment of the future European Commission, and its proposal for post-2027 policies- for Europe’s next decade. To begin, he asked panelists to look back and reflect on the achievements obtained for mountains over the last policy cycle.

Panelists emphasised that mountains’ uniqueness is recognised and receives special attention from the European Union, particularly through **Article 174 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union** and the **Cohesion Policy**. In addition to this article, the **EU’s Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas** (introduced by the European Commission in 2021) succeeded in promoting a vision of rural areas – including mountains – as places of opportunities rather than places of constraints. Mountain needs have also been addressed by other instruments related to rural development in the Common Agricultural Policy (e.g. 5% minimum spending for Areas with Natural Constraints, LEADER/CLLD approach), and specific funding under the Horizon 2020/Europe calls.

Mr. Nadler illustrated that, as emerged from the **9th Cohesion Report’s** dedicated chapter on mountains, **many mountain regions are performing below the EU average**, experiencing declining GDP and low socio-economic performance. He also added that evidence

from the report shows a stable population in mountain areas, mainly due to incoming elderly inhabitants, but an **overall loss of working-age population.**

“This Commission shifted the perspective on rural and remote areas to integrate a rural dimension through the EU’s Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, defining an integrated and connected approach. COVID-19 showed us the value of living in remote areas, and we believe this will continue”

Toma Šutić

The demographic challenges experienced by remote regions have been at the core of the 2019 appointed **Vice President on Demography and Democracy of the European Commission**. Mr. Šutić emphasised the importance of this Cabinet for its ability to promote the horizontality of policies and commended that such work should be continued by a European agency on demography.

Panelists stressed the importance of engaging local actors to plan for inclusive and territorial-just post-2027 policies. Ms. Pavić-Rogošić particularly stressed the importance of **rural proofing** and even **youth proofing** – as recently introduced by the [EESC Youth Test](#) – and commended the continuation of rural networking and **community empowerment through the Rural Pact**.

Furthermore, Ms. Frizon Somogy drew attention to the need for more **granular data and indicators** to build evidence for future policies and bridge the current data gaps. The data gap echoed across all panelists, who highlighted the potential of AI and digital technologies to gather data below NUTS3 data.

For post-2027 policies to address the needs of mountains, panelists called for policy simplification and the implementation of territorial impact assessment, breaking policy silos, and further research to address mountain sustainability along all three pillars (social, environmental, economic). They insisted on the need to implement existing mechanisms through horizontal interactions at European level (cross-DGs synergies) and multi-level cooperation.

“It’s not always about new mechanisms but using existing ones”

Benoit Nadler

A Policy Roadmap for Rural and Mountain Futures

Mark REDMAN
Director at Highclere Consulting

The **MOVING Policy Roadmap** is one of the main project's contributions to post-2027 policies due to its relevance in untapping the potential of Mountain Value Chains. Mark Redman underlined the usefulness of using Policy Roadmap as a **strategic tool for structuring, planning, and communicating proposed actions and initiatives**, including policy recommendations. It provides flexibility to support various forms of transformation and other development processes, especially useful for facilitating transformations affecting multiple policy areas.

The MOVING Policy Roadmap was constructed across a set of **needs-driven policy building blocks** thanks to **"collective intelligence"** of approximately 1,000 stakeholders in a total of 23 mountainous regions around Europe, located in 11 EU Member States, 3 EU candidate countries (North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey), plus Scotland and Switzerland.

Eight key needs were identified by MOVING and used to derive the **eight Policy Building Blocks** of the project's Roadmap. **Policy Building Blocks** represent **clusters of interventions, structures, processes and working methods that can facilitate improvements**

in policy coherence and are applicable to national/regional context regardless of their administrative and political traditions.

The eight needs/building blocks of the Roadmap are:

- To implement better governance and regulation of mountains
- To foster cohesion and influence through collaboration and networking
- To build capacity (human, institutional) for greater agency (to act, influence)
- To ensure mountain livelihoods for all (inclusive economic development)
- To sustain use of local assets/resources
- To build capacities to mitigate/adapt to changing contexts
- To better balance ecological integrity and social well-being

"Mechanisms to strengthen mountain governance remain elusive but benefit from approaches that fit local contexts while building equitable and creative collaborations among diverse, supportive actors within and beyond mountain communities"

Mark Redman

Strengthening governance was set as an all-encompassing Policy Block to deliver the MOVING Roadmap. In fact, as Mr. Redman emphasised, reinforcing local governance and institutions at the level of mountain Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) allows for building a more favorable policy framework (conducive policy environments) and "unlocking the power" of mountain product value chains (food, drink, and rural tourism). He also pointed out that strong local governance can make constructive differences in the well-being of residents, as evidenced by several tools such as the LEADER/CLLD approach.

To conclude, Mr. Redman explained that short-medium and long-term recommendations were derived for each of the Policy Building Block, which were further validated through partners' and Value Chains' feedback. The MOVING Policy Roadmap will be published in the coming few months and shared with the EU institutions and key stakeholders.

Round table | From the Roadmap to Practice

Moderated by Mark Redman, Director at Highclere Consulting

**Gustavo LÓPEZ
CUTILLAS**

**REGI Committee
Secretariat, European
Parliament**

**Guillaume
CORRADINO**

Euromontana

**Erik
GLØERSEN**

**Senior
Consultant,
Spatial Foresight**

**Urszula
BUDZICH TABOR**

**Senior Policy
Analyst, Rural Pact
Support Office**

This round table aimed at gathering expert and stakeholders' feedback on the MOVING Policy Roadmap for "unlocking the power" of Mountain Value Chains and discussing how to operationalise it.

"MOVING Policy Roadmap provides a narrative for work in the mountains in the coming years and there is still work to be done to connect the value chain with rural development and mountain areas"

Guillaume Corradino

Panelists praised the work done by MOVING in its capacity to build its Roadmap, **embedding the concept of functional areas and formulating recommendations through wide stakeholder participation**. They also underlined that this Roadmap is timely as it comes at the moment of negotiations for the post-2027 policies and provides arguments to show the added value of place-based and decentralised policies. Ms. Budzich Tabor said that the conclusions of the MOVING Roadmap – in terms of needs and Building Blocks – are mostly confirming what emerged from the Rural Pact workshops and Community.

Panelists underlined **several challenges** arising from transferring these similar objectives into practice, such as the changing Parliament at European level and shifting European priorities, the need to build a message which is understandable by all stakeholders (policy, science, society) and supported by strong evidence, and the lack of capacity to support the change from those implementing existing policies and programmes.

Mr. Corradino highlighted that Euromontana is committed to building

groups of policy-makers and actors advocating for sustainable mountain development at European level, as well as at national levels, for instance through their daily policy work and the next [European Mountain Convention](#). Other governance mechanisms, such as the **Rural Pact** – and the **Rural Pact Community Group on Mountains** – or **Interreg projects** were mentioned as tools to promote knowledge exchange and collaboration. Additionally, the role of **'soft territorial cooperation'** was referred to as a precise iterative technique to work with actors, focusing on issues and building stronger territories without adding additional rules while allowing for a flexible approach.

Mr. López Cutillas underlined the need to ensure the implementation of **policies promoting integrated territorial development**. He added that such policies already exist, yet their uptake should be strengthened.

"Value Chains are functional areas by definition. I am very pleased that the MOVING Policy Roadmap takes a value chain, functional area approach which is missing in current policies"

Erik Gløersen

Furthermore, panelists pointed out the need **to engage with national and regional actors to make use of existing funds or advocate for budget interventions for mountains at the regional/national level**. They also stressed that simpler rules, higher funding rates for community-led development, and capacity-building activities are key steps to lead towards a better uptake of existing tools while ensuring low administrative burdens on final beneficiaries.

DAY 2 | 14 JUNE 2024

Closing of the conference

Mar DELGADO

Full Professor at University of Cordoba and MOVING Coordinator

“This is not the end of MOVING, but the start of a better future for EU policies for mountain areas post-2027”

Mar Delgado

Mar Delgado closed the conference by thanking all the project's partners and stakeholders who contributed to making the project a success, as well as the conference speakers and attendees. As she underlined, the project's impacts and commitment to more

sustainable mountains will not end with the official end of MOVING but will continue through the dedicated actions of all actors who contributed to it.

MOVING MAIN OUTCOMES

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